

ISic1331

I.Sicily inscription 1331

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140827

1. Ὠραία
2. χρηστὰ □ καὶ
3. ἄμεμπτε
4. χαῖρε.
5. Γάμε □ χρηστὲ
6. καὶ □ ἄμεμ-
7. πτε □ χαῖρε.
8. Οὐρβανίων
9. Γόνγε
10. χρηστὲ □ καὶ
11. ἄμεμπτε
12. χαῖρε.
- 13.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492939

EDCS 39101704

PHI 140827

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0510 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Castelli, Gabriele Lancillotto, principe di Torremuzza 1769. Siciliae et objacentium insularum veterum inscriptionum nova collectio. Panormus. At cl.14 no.85

Castelli, Gabriello Lancellotto, Principe di Torremuzza 1784. Siciliae et objacentium insularum veterum inscriptionum nova collectio prolegomenis et notis illustrata, et iterum cum emendationibus, & auctariis evulgata. Palermo. At cl.14 no.100

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